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Catalogue of services

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ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AgroServ	Integrated services supporting a sustainable Agroecological transition (AgroServ)
API	Application Programming Interface
ARIA	Access to Research Infrastructure Administration
CatRIS	Catalogue of Research Infrastructure Services
CWE	Collaborative Working Environment
ENVRI	Community of Environmental Research Infrastructures working together towards an integrated Earth system science
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategic Framework for Research Infrastructure
GDPR	General data protection regulation
IRISCC	Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change
ISIA	Information System for Infrastructure Administration
M4C	MICROBES-4-CLIMATE, Microbial services addressing climate change risks for biodiversity and for agricultural and forestry ecosystems: enabling curiosity-driven research and advancing frontier knowledge
MERIL	Mapping of the European Research Infrastructure Landscape
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RI	Research Infrastructure
TNA	Transnational Access
URI	Unique Resource Identifier (URI)
WP	Work Package

Concept	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface is a way for two or more computer programs or components to communicate with each other
Metadata schema	The metadata schema lists the data elements with their definitions. In addition, it states the rules that govern the use of each specific data elements to describe a resource
REST API	Application Programming Interface (API) that conforms to the design principles of the representational state transfer (REST) architectural style
Search filter	Pre-made search strategy with keywords and/or relevant groupings to aid the user in finding the most relevant information
URI	Unique Resource Identifier is a unique combination of characters that identifies an abstract or physical resource
Vocabulary	In science, the language used for a specific field of expertise

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About the project

Terrestrial biodiversity and ecosystems are being challenged by climate change and environmental degradation. Moreover, threats to agricultural and forestry systems represent some of the most serious environmental and socio-economic menaces that the planet and humanity are facing. Climate change is recognized as a major hindrance to the regulation of global natural cycles, affecting biodiversity and exacerbating the loss of ecosystem services, which should be tackled simultaneously. Microorganisms, despite being overlooked and not usually considered in the context of climate change, are key for the healthy maintenance of the biosphere. The impacts of climate change on the assembly, functions and occurrence of microbiomes are still not wholly understood. The rather intricate interactions and relations between microorganisms, plants and soil, their impacts on crop (plant) productivity, health and efficiency, and how they are impacted by climate change are still largely unknown. The inner functioning of ecosystems remains mostly unmapped, and the microbiome's influence on climate change mitigation and adaptation poorly understood. MICROBES-4-CLIMATE (M4C) intends to provide the global community of researchers ease of access to a selected cluster of Research Infrastructures and their integrated services, coupled with training and scientific and/or technical support. The M4C project stands out as a Transnational Access programme, which will offer users the possibility to conduct research leveraging microorganisms and ecosystems' interactions and explore their roles in climate change resilience, mitigation and adaptation. This high-quality access will drive new frontiers of knowledge and incentivize applied research for harnessing plant-microbiome interactions to improve the climate resiliency of plants/crops. This could ultimately bolster the resilience and sustainability of food systems.

Executive Summary

The overall objective of M4C WP1 is to design, establish, and maintain the project's catalogue of services. The M4C catalogue of services is the main reference for the users and the single source of consistent information on all operational services offered to conduct research leveraging microorganisms and ecosystems' interactions and their roles in climate change resilience, mitigation, and adaptation. The services will be made available to users in the M4C project via transnational access.

The design of the M4C catalogue of services is based on the ISIA platform. This application, developed and maintained by CNRS, France (<https://isia.cnrs.fr/>), currently hosts the service catalogues of other RIs and projects. However, some adaptations are required to meet the needs of M4C, which will be shown throughout the report.

A new challenge in M4C will be the integration of the service catalogue hosted on ISIA within the Collaborative Working Environment (CWE) Platform managing user access to M4C services. The M4C CWE is operated by LifeWatch-ERIC and constitutes an online, centralized access management platform providing four main functionalities, i.e., access to (i) data and services, (ii) expert consulting, (iii) Transnational Access (TNA) programme, and (iv) training. This report identifies adaptations needed for the integration of the catalogue of services into the CWE to optimize user access and discovery of the M4C services.

During the project, the development of the M4C catalogue of services will be an iterative process between M4C work package activities and service developments and the web interface developers. This report is, therefore, not exhaustive, but describes the primary design of the first release version of the M4C catalogue of services. Concurrently, the technical solution for the integration of ISIA into the CWE has been initiated. Besides, training sessions for installation managers, who will be responsible for populating the online web catalogue with the description of the services and the installations, are ongoing.

Chapter 1

Objectives

Objective of this report

Work Package 1 aims to establish a common service/resource catalogue framework for describing and offering RI services/resources in a user-friendly searchable format. In particular, WP1 aims to design and implement catalogues and software tools to operationalize the integration and customisation of services available to users across different disciplines and all M4C RIs. It should enable interdisciplinary research by enabling higher levels of integration of multi-RI services.

In meeting this overall objective, D1.1 shows the design of the M4C catalogues describing the installations and their service/resources available to carry out TNA projects, and making them findable and accessible to researchers, research groups, communities, projects, organisations, innovators and businesses, funders and policy makers. The deliverable describes the work undertaken in Task 1.3 and the current developmental status of the catalogues of services and installations, a key service of M4C facilitating structuration and improving the quality of services offered within single RIs and across multiple RIs. It promotes efficient and multi-inter-transdisciplinary research offering new opportunities to users, new tools to RI managers, and new communication strategies for RI communities. This task also works towards a common service/resource definition model and service/resource management for RIs to reach a harmonized approach to service/resource catalogues.

As part of the AgroServ network, a working group evaluated the technologies, methodologies and experiences from CatRIS and EOSC, which are the current reference catalogues for research infrastructures, installations and services. As a result, a service and an installation description model that is compatible and interoperable with these existing catalogues was provided, including:

- A tool for collecting and updating metadata with a controlled vocabulary on the general description of RIs, their service offerings, resources and availability, with great accessibility for installation managers;
- An online catalogue of research installations, accessible to all user profiles to discover and use the full potential of European agroecological research.

This collection and centralisation of information will support the development of TNA project applications. Applying standard service and installation description models in the M4C catalogues will ensure compatibility and interoperability with major catalogues like the EOSC marketplace. The APIs provided by these catalogues allow automatic information updates without requiring installation managers to connect to them. It is then important to use a standardized vocabulary to annotate entries in a consistent, structured format, allowing data to be seamlessly processed by other catalogues through APIs and to provide it in machine-readable formats that can be used to feed Deep Learning.

D1.1 outputs:

- Define the whole procedure for project evaluation and optimization, from the application portal to the fulfilment of access requirements, including TNA. The catalogues will improve the discovery of resources for users and increase the visibility of M4C network services. Therefore, they are the entry points for project leaders to prepare their applications and start the evaluation and optimization process. The catalogues will provide links to the network's project submission form (WP5).
- Harmonize the data management rules across the network, ensuring the catalogues comply with common data management requirements, particularly GDPR (WP5).
- Enable integration with EOSC marketplace catalogue and CatRIs, besides the display of the catalogues through M4C communication tools, especially the M4C website (www.microbes4climate.eu) (WP8).

The development of the M4C catalogue of services will build on already existing service catalogues from M4C beneficiaries, founding the basis for further development.

To meet the expectations, the ISIA platform developed and maintained at [CNRS, France](http://www.cnrs.fr), was chosen to host the catalogue of installations and their linked services. The ISIA platform currently hosts the catalogues of [AnaEE France](http://www.anaee.fr), [AnaEE ERIC](http://www.anaee-eric.fr) and the EU INFRA-SERV projects [AgroServ](http://www.agroserv.eu) and [IRISCC](http://www.iriscc.eu). The AgroServ project already provides a catalogue of services across multiple RIs, some of them equal to those offered by M4C. Therefore, the new ISIA version of this network has served as the reference model for the design of the M4C catalogues of services and installations. However, some adaptations are being implemented, such as improvements on the search filter options and the development of an online web interface for service providers to allow updating required information (preferably by filling out and uploading a .csv template or similar with all mandatory data fields).

Chapter 2

Tasks Implementation

2. Tasks Implementation

The M4C catalogues will be based on the same required functions defined for the AgroServ catalogue:

- collect information about installations and their services in a single distributed tool
- facilitate the use of standard description models compatible with the main existing catalogues
- control the vocabulary used to improve data discovery, interoperability and reuse
- automate the updating of data in the different catalogues
- display information on a web page accessible to all, keeping a level of information adapted to all user profiles
- facilitate the discovery of suppliers and services in a catalogue accessible online to the general public
- facilitate the discovery of suppliers and services in a catalogue offering filters on the different description data
- guide users to M4C communication tools and project submission portal

2.1 Development of the catalogues

2.1.1 Data collection

WP1 task 1.3 has designed and developed catalogues providing an overview and entry point for the hierarchical discovery of the four M4C RIs and four research institutions organized in 42 installations and distributed in 12 European countries.

To collect all information concerning installations and their services, CNRS has developed a distributed tool that is accessible to all installation managers called ISIA (Information System for Infrastructure Administration).

ISIA is a web-based application accessible through any internet browser. It provides an interface for users to manage their resources and projects. Each installation has its own application with a dedicated configuration adapted to its activity. All the installations are then connected to the same network with common functionalities such as a project submission form, a central hub to receive and evaluate all the projects submitted to the network, and forms for entering information about the installations and services. It should be noted that a service provider may be part of several networks, each with different configurations (no Central Hub, different evaluation processes, different models for describing installations and services, etc.) (Figure 1).

Figure 1 ISIA – A distributed architecture

Service providers have, therefore, an interface dedicated to their own installations to which only invited managers have access. They are also able to update information about installations and services via dedicated forms, as it can be seen in Figures 2 to 6.

Figure 2 ISIA - Access to installation information

Figure 3 ISIA - Networks installation description forms

Figure 4 ISIA - Installation information entry form

The screenshot displays the ISIA web application interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Projects', 'Resource', and 'Config' dropdowns, a search bar containing 'EcogenO', and user profile icons. The main content area is titled 'EOSC Services Data Model Description'. On the left, a sidebar under 'Service descriptions' shows 'ARGo' as the selected service. The main area lists several expandable sections, each with a plus icon: 'Basic Information', 'Marketing Information', 'Marketing Information Multimedia', 'Marketing Information Use Cases', 'Dependencies Information', 'Classification Information - Description', and 'Keywords'.

Figure 5 ISIA - Networks services description forms

This screenshot shows the 'Marketing Information Multimedia' section expanded within the 'EOSC Services Data Model Description' form. The table below shows the following data:

Multimedia Name	Multimedia
ARGo1	https://libb.co/2j9DgJl

A plus icon is located at the bottom right of the table area, indicating the option to add new multimedia entries.

Figure 6 ISIA - Service information entry form

The forms depicted in Figures 2 to 6 are the single-entry point for entering installation and service information and allow automatic dissemination to the various catalogues: M4C, EOSC, CatRIs and any other catalogue with an API to automatically update the data.

2.1.2 Catalogues and description sheets of installations and services

In the main catalogues, the information displayed will correspond to what the installation manager entered in the EOSC description template forms. For the M4C catalogues, we have decided to display the additional information used in AgroServ, allowing users to better identify the most suitable installation or service for their project. For example, it seems essential for a user to know the hosting capacities of the installation such as an experimental field site or the daily analysis capacities for a chemical analysis. The catalogues have a "classic" homepage (Figures 7 & 8) to avoid losing users who already have reference points in the main catalogues. It also includes a list of maps corresponding to each installation and service (Figure 9), and filters to refine the search (Figure 10).

Figure 7 ISIA – M4C installation catalogue homepage

Figure 8 ISIA – M4C service catalogue homepage

Figure 9 ISIA – M4C catalogues map

Service catalog / Ecotron IleDeFrance - Ecolabs

Ecotron IleDeFrance – Ecolabs

Your Ecosystem, your Controlled Conditions

General description

The Ecotron IleDeFrance is based on technologies implemented in the Ecolab equipment and developed primarily in collaboration with the French private company Cesbron. The Ecolab is a modular structure coupling together three environmental chambers and one laboratory room. Each environmental chamber can be independently controlled accurately for realistic climate and atmospheric conditions (temperature, humidity, CO2 and O2 content, lighting) with unprecedented power and accuracy. A stainless steel lysimeter with temperature-control on three independent levels makes it possible to incubate both terrestrial and aquatic systems and simulate thermal gradients. Artificial light can be provided with several technologies to adapt to the needs and constraints of each project. The Ecotron IleDeFrance combines several Ecolabs into a network making it possible to run powerful, replicated experiments.

Specific informations

Both Ecotron IleDeFrance and Ecotron de Montpellier are part of the distributed "Infrastructure de Recherche" (IR) managed and supported by CNRS and Ecole normale supérieure since 2010. Ecotrons enable highly controlled manipulation and measurement of terrestrial and aquatic organisms, communities and ecosystems with unprecedented power and quality. On a technological side, an Ecotron is defined as a device allowing the precise conditioning of the environment and the detailed acquisition of data and activities of organisms and ecosystems. Ecotrons structure the process of forest landscape development.

Provider
CEREEP - Ecotron IDF

Organisation
CNRS

Installation Catalog
Ecotron IleDeFrance - Ecolabs

Climatic chamber Temperature control Hygrometry control Ecotron CO2 control AnaEE-France
Environmental monitoring facilities Fofjuf air air humidity air temperature aquatic mesocosm

Samuel Abiven
Ecotron IDF scientific director

[Send an email](#) ecotron@bio.ens.psl.eu

[Visit our website](#) https://www.cereep.bio.ens.psl.eu/

Figure 10 ISIA – Example of a M4C installation description page

The M4C catalogues are available at the following addresses:

- [Installations](#)
- [Services](#)

2.2 Scientific and technical interoperability

2.2.1 Assistance with controlled vocabulary input

A controlled vocabulary from thesauri is essential for interoperability between tools, disciplines and users. It guarantees an unambiguous understanding of the content and grants a Unique Resource Identifier (URI) that machines can use. To support this, ISIA offers service managers a tool that suggests terms from thesauri, ensuring the information they enter is reusable by both humans and machines. Each term entered will have an associated URI. Ontology-based tools will make it possible to link these terms in machine-readable RDF-type formats, increasing the discovery capabilities of search engines and, consequently, the visibility of the information.

2.2.2 Automatic connection with other catalogues

By using the EOSC supplier and service description model, we ensure interoperability between our catalogues and the other catalogues developed using this model. CatRIs has already set up a REST API to synchronize data from the EOSC catalogue and populate the same catalogue with information from new suppliers and services. We will leverage the experience gained in synchronising the data collected in the

ISIA application to create REST APIs for each catalogue where our installations and services need to be visible.

The implementation of these synchronizations is scheduled for the second half of 2025 and a specific documentation will be provided to detail the methods and commands used. The other catalogues will then be able to use the APIs developed to harvest the data collected and to authorize an ever-greater openness to discovery by machines. For this, we will use the experience acquired by CatRIs to provide data in RDF format and a dedicated API, based on the model provided by EOSC and using Web Ontology Language (OWL). These RDF graphs will be enriched by the URIs collected during the proposal of terms from controlled vocabularies as described in the previous paragraph. These RDF descriptions will not only contribute and encourage discovery, interoperability and interdisciplinarity, but also allow a more efficient reuse of the data produced.

2.3 Users’ journey through the catalogues

As depicted in Figure 11, there are several users of the M4C catalogues. Research teams and evaluation managers will consult the catalogue to find the most suitable service, while installation managers will have to update information about their services and their installation.

Figure 11 ISIA – Users’ journey map

Collaboration with M4C WP5 ensures that the research teams' journey through the CWE will be as smooth as possible. The catalogues play a key role in linking the service offers of each installation and the construction of multi-RI projects for TNA applications (M4C WP4). Review stages with installation managers help validate the feasibility of the projects regarding technical aspects, resources and availability.

Chapter 3

The MICROBES-4-CLIMATE Metadata Schema

3 The MICROBES-4-CLIMATE Metadata Schema

The M4C metadata schema will be adapted from the existing AgroServ metadata schemas (Figures 12 to 15). While all data fields in the EOSC model from the AgroServ project (Figure 12 and 14) can be accepted in the context of M4C, only a subset of these will be categorized as mandatory, while others will be categorized as optional. There are two existing schemas in AgroServ and M4C, one for the installations (Figures 12 and 13) and one for the services (Figures 14 and 15). The tables following each figure provide the description of each metadata field.

The metadata schema for M4C services should be compatible with the corresponding schemas used in EOSC and related projects and activities. However, the EOSC Future project deprecated this profile in favour of a service profile dedicated to digital services. Alignment is needed between EOSC Beyond (successor of EOSC Future), ENVRI-Hub NEXT (<https://envri.eu/envri-hub-next/>), and other projects to reach a consensus, potentially for the 2nd or 3rd release of the M4C catalogue of services. Until then, M4C will work with the existing metadata schema of AgroServ.

3.1 EOSC Model - Installations

Figure 12 EOSC model used by the ISIA platform for the catalogue describing the facilities that provide services

3.1.1 Basic Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
ID	A persistent identifier, a unique reference to the Provider	String (max 30 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	No	Delivered by EOSC Catalogue
Abbreviation	An abbreviation of the Provider Name as assigned by the Provider	String (max 30 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	AnaEE - Central Hub
Name	Full Name of the Provider/Organisation offering the resource and acting as the main contact point.	String (max 100 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Analysis and Experimentations on Ecosystems
Website	The website with information about the Provider.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://www.anaee.eu/
Legal Entity	A Y/N question to define whether the Provider is a Legal Entity or not.	Boolean	One	Mandatory	Yes	No	Yes
Legal Status	The legal status of the Provider. The legal status is usually noted in the registration act/statutes. For independent legal entities (1) - legal status of the Provider. For embedded providers (2) - legal status of the hosting legal entity. It is also possible to select Not a legal entity.	List of controlled values	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)
Hosting Legal Entity	Name of the organisation/institution legally hosting (housing) the provider/research infrastructure or its coordinating centre. A distinction is made between: (1) research infrastructures that are self-standing and have a defined and distinct legal entity, (2) research infrastructures that are embedded into another institution which is a legal entity (such as a university, a research organisation, etc.). If (1) - name of the research infrastructure, If (2) - name of the hosting organisation.	String (max 100 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	No	Research infrastructures that is self-standing and have a defined and distinct legal entity

3.1.2 Marketing Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Description	A high-level description of the Provider in fairly non-technical terms, with the vision, mission, objectives, background, experience.	String (max 1000 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	AnaEE (Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems) will pave the way for understanding the complex impact of today's multiple, interacting global change drivers on terrestrial and aquatic continental ecosystems across Europe. It will forge evidence-based adaptation and mitigation strategies that assure plant, soil, water, biodiversity and ecosystem health today and in the future. Characteristic of AnaEE, its versatile facilities that can simulate environmental drivers from land-use change, pollution, biological invasions, rising atmospheric greenhouse gases concentrations, and increasing extreme events such as droughts and heatwaves. AnaEE will link its facilities with an array of user communities, including scientists, land managers, the bio-economy industry and policy makers, to minimize human environmental impact and maximize societal benefits in a dynamic world. Specificity of AnaEE is to integrate, in a single, distributed RI, experimental methods, modelling and experimentation.
Logo	Link to the logo/visual identity of the Provider.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://i.postimg.cc/FHcsQ5WY/logo-anaee-web.png
Multimedia	Link to video, slideshow, photos, screenshots with details of the Provider.	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://www.anaee.eu/
Multimedia Name	Short description of the Multimedia content	String (max 100 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	AnaEE Website

3.1.3 Classification Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Scientific Domain	A named group of providers that offer access to the same type of resource or capabilities.	List of controlled values (see Appendix Table 1)	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Agricultural Sciences, Natural Sciences, Social Sciences
Scientific Sub-domain	A named group of providers that offer access to the same type of resource or capabilities, within the defined domain.	List of controlled values (see Appendix Table 1)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Agricultural Biotechnology, Agriculture, Forestry & Fisheries, Animal & Dairy Sciences, Other Agricultural Sciences, Veterinary Sciences, Earth & Related Environmental Sciences, Environmental Engineering, Biological Sciences, Chemical Sciences
Tags	Keywords associated with the Provider to simplify search by relevant keywords.	String (max 20 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Analysis, Experimentation, Ecosystem, terrestrial, aquatic, ...
Structure Type	Defines the Provider structure type (single-sited, distributed, mobile, virtual, etc.)	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 2)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Distributed, physical, virtual, mobile

3.1.4 Location Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Street Name and Number	Street and Number of in-corporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 50 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Campus CNRS 1 avenue de la terrasse
Postal Code	Postal code of in-corporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 20 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	91190
City	City of incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 20 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Gif-sur-Yvette
Region	Region of in-corporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 50 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Ile de France
Country	Country of in-corporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 3)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	France

3.1.5 Contact Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Main contact/Provider Manager - First Name	First Name of the Provider's main contact person/Provider Manager.	String (max 20 words)	One	Mandatory	No	No	Michel
Main contact/Provider Manager - Last Name	Last Name of the Provider's main contact person/Provider Manager.	String (max 20 words)	One	Optional	No	No	Boer
Main contact/Provider Manager - Email	Email of the Provider's main contact person/Provider manager.	Email	One	Mandatory	No	No	michel.boer@anaee.eu
Main contact/Provider Manager - Phone	Phone of the Provider's main contact person/Provider manager.	String (max 20 words)	One	Optional	No	No	+33(0)677020295
Main contact/Provider Manager - Position	Position of the Provider's main contact person/Provider manager.	String (max 50 words)	One	Optional	No	No	Director General
Public contact - First Name	First Name of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Michel
Public contact - Last Name	Last Name of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Boer
Public contact - Email	Email of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal or general email to contact Provider.	Email	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	michel.boer@anaee.eu
Public contact - Phone	Phone of the provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal or general phone to contact the Provider.	String (max 20 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	+33(0)677020295
Public contact - Position	Position of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 50 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Director General

3.1.6 Maturity Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Life Cycle Status	Current status of the Provider/Research infrastructure life-cycle.	List of controlled values	One	Optional	Yes	No	Operation
Certifications	List of certifications obtained for the Provider (including the certification body and any certificate number).	String (max 250 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	AGROSERV: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01, ENVRI FAIR, EHRIITC

3.1.7 Dependencies Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Participating Countries	Providers/Research Infrastructures that are funded by several countries should list here all supporting countries (including the Coordinating country).	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 3)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Italy
Affiliations	Providers that are members or affiliated or associated with other organisations should list those organisations here	String (max 30 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	https://www.anaee.eu/about/national-nodes
Networks	Providers that are members of networks should list those networks here.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	AgroServ, ENVRI
Catalogue	The Catalogue this Provider is originally registered at.	Catalogue ID	1	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/platform/list/agroserv

3.1.8 Other Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
ESFRI Domain	ESFRI domain classification.	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 4)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Environment
ESFRI Type	If the research infrastructure is (part of) an ESFRI project indicate how the RI participates: a) is a node of an ESFRI project, b) is an ESFRI project, c) is an ESFRI landmark, d) is not an ESFRI project or landmark.	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 5)	One	Optional	Yes	No	Landmark
MERIL Scientific Domain	MERIL scientific domain classification	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Earth & Environmental Sciences
MERIL Scientific Sub-domain	MERIL scientific sub-domain classification	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Agronomy, Forestry, Plant Breeding Centres, Analytical Facilities, In Situ Earth Observatories, Conceptual Models
Areas of Activity	Basic research, Applied research or Technological development	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 6)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Applied Research, Basic Research, Technological Development, Other
Societal Grand Challenges	Provider's participation in the grand societal challenges as defined by the European Commission	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 7)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Environment, Europe in a changing world, Natural Resources
Sustainable Development Goals	Provider's contribute to the sustainable development goals as defined by European Commission	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 8)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Zero hunger, Clean water and sanitation, Sustainable cities and communities, Responsible consumption and production, Climate action, Life below water, Life on land

National Roadmaps	Provider's participation in a national roadmap.	String (max 80 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c6647f05-874e-4cdd-af70-22ade4759930/language-en
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3.2 Metadata fields for Additional Information - Installations

Additional Information				
Basic & Marketing Information	Keywords	Experimental platform Information	Analytical platform Information	Modelling platform Information
Main Image Submission project link Affiliation laboratory Research Institution Platform capacity Accomodation capacity Electricity Wifi HighSpeed Wifi Shower	List of keywords Location Information Latitude Longitude Country abbreviation	Experimental platform type Climate Zones Ecosystems Environmental Controlled Factors Environmental Manipulated Factors Replication capacity HighSpeed Wifi Shower	Analytical platform type Analysis categories Analysed parameters Instruments used Precision and sensitivity Analytical capacity	

Figure 13 The M4C metadata fields for additional information on facilities that provide services

3.2.1 Basic and Marketing Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Main image for the descriptive sheet	This image will appear at the top of the description sheet and will be representative of the installation.	String (max 30 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://i.postimg.cc/BbT9V4Q3/le-chateau-de-button-a-gif-sur-yvette-le-31-juillet-2015-1.jpg
Submission project link	Link to your network's project submission form with the selected installation.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://isia.cnrs.fr/ppa/agroserv/agroser vpreproposal
Affiliation laboratory	Name of your affiliate laboratory	String (max 100 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://www.anaee.eu/about/national-nodes
Research institution	Name of your Research institution	String (max 100 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://www.anaee.eu/about/national-nodes
Installation capacity	Number and designation of available experimental units	String (max 100 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	0
Accommodation capacity	Number of accommodations available	String (max 100 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	0
Electricity	Power supply available on the installation	Boolean	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Yes
Wifi	Wifi available on the installation	Boolean	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Yes
Highspeed Wifi	High-speed Wi-Fi available on the installation	Boolean	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Yes
Shower	Shower available on the installation	Boolean	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	No

3.2.2 Keywords

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Keywords	Keywords about your installation	String (max 1000 words)	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Analysis, Experimentation, Ecosystems, terrestrial, aquatic, ...

3.2.3 Location and Country

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Latitude	Latitude coordinate of the installation (in decimals: 60.924530 for 60°55'8.3"N)	String (7 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	48.704754
Longitude	Longitude coordinate of the installation (in decimals: 11.451259 for 1127°04.5"E)	String (7 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	2.135254
Country Code	Country name abbreviation (France: FR)	Controlled values	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	FR

3.2.4 Experimental Installations

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Experimental Installation Type	Enclosed, Open air or Observation	Controlled values	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Open air
Climate Zones	Climates that can be found on the installation	Controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Mediterranean
Ecosystems	Ecosystems that can be found on the installation	Controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Grassland
Environmental Controlled Factors	Environmental parameters measured on the installation	Controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Atmospheric temperature, humidity,

							soil water content, soil temperature, ...
Environmental Manipulated Factors	Environmental parameters that can be manipulated on the installation	Controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	precipitation, nutrients, ...
Replication Capacity	Number of experimental units available	String (max 100 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	16

3.2.5 Analytical Installations

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Analytical Installation Type	Stable or Mobile	Controlled values	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Mobile
Categories	Analysis categories that can be found on the installation	Controlled values	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Isotopes
Analysed Parameters	Parameters that can be analysed on the installation	Controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	13CO2
Instrument Used	Instruments used to analyse this parameter on the installation	String (max 100 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Picarro G2401
Precision and Sensitivity	Instrument precision and sensitivity	String (max 100 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	10 to 50 ppb
Analytical Capacity	Number of analysis you can realize (ex : 1000 per day)	String (max 100 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Max sampling frequency: 5s 4 analyzers

3.3 EOOSC Model - Services

Figure 14 EOOSC model used by the ISIA platform for the M4C catalogue describing the services provided

3.3.1 Basic Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
ID	A persistent identifier, a unique reference to the Service/Resource in the context of the EOSC Portal.	String (max 30 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	No	Delivered by EOSC Catalogue
Abbreviation	An abbreviation of the Service/Resource Name as assigned by the Provider	String (Max 20 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	AE - VRE
Name	Service/Resource Full Name as assigned by the Provider.	String (max 80 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Agroecology Virtual Research Environment
Service/Resource Organisation	The name (or abbreviation) of the organisation that manages or delivers the service/resource, or that coordinates resource delivery in a federated scenario.	Provider ID	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	LifeWatch ERIC
Service/Resource Providers	The name(s) (or abbreviation(s)) of Provider(s) that manage or deliver the Service/Resource in federated scenarios.	Provider IDs	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	LifeWatch ERIC
Webpage	Webpage with information about the Service/Resource usually hosted and maintained by the Provider.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://www.lifewatch.eu

3.3.2 Marketing Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Description	A high-level description in fairly non-technical terms of a) what the Service/Resource does, the functionality it provides and Service/Resources it enables to access, b) the benefit to a user/customer delivered by a Resource; benefits are usually related to alleviating pains (e.g., eliminate undesired outcomes, obstacles or risks) or producing gains (e.g. increased performance, social gains, positive emotions or cost saving), c) list of customers, communities, users, etc. using the Resource.	String (max 1000 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	<p>Lifewatch ERIC is a European Research Infrastructure that provides e-Science research facilities to scientists, with a thematic focus on biodiversity, ecosystem functions and services research, including agroecology. Lifewatch ERIC achieves this by providing access to a multitude of resources and services that enable researchers to conduct their work and drive innovation.</p> <p>One of these services is the design and implementation of a Virtual Research Environment (VRE). A VRE is a web-based workspace that provides data users with a comprehensive suite of services and tools to support their data-related work. These tools include centralized access to data, data processing, visualisation of data, sharing of results, and other e-services. By using a VRE, data-users can work more efficiently with data, collaborate more effectively with other data-users stakeholders, and generate new knowledge in their field.</p> <p>In agroecology, a VRE provides data users with a platform for networking, data gathering and integration, data analysis and visualisation and artificial intelligence (AI) deep learning. The VRE allows data-users to identify and engage with their community while gathering and integrating data from various sources. The VRE offers computing power through high data analysis capacities such as the Picasso supercomputing centre, as well as storage capacity and data maintenance. Data users can also replicate and share the processes of data</p>

							<p>analysis, including workflows, models, and algorithms. Additionally, the VRE supports the use of Artificial intelligence (AI), deep learning and digital twins for more advanced research. The VRE in agroecology could also offer training and capacity building opportunities and facilitate dissemination and communication of research findings to relevant stakeholders.</p> <p>Using a VRE provides many benefits to the agroecology community. These benefits include improved efficiency and collaboration, access to advanced computing resources, the ability to analyse and visualize data in new and innovative ways, and the potential for increased research productivity and impact.</p>
Tagline	Short catch-phrase for marketing and advertising purposes. It will be usually displayed close to the Resource name and should refer to the main value or purpose of the Resource.	String (max 100 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Unleashing the data-users potential with Lifewatch ERIC's Virtual Research Environments - the ultimate tool for seamless collaboration and data-driven innovation in Agroecology
Logo	Link to the logo/visual identity of the Resource. The logo will be visible at the Portal. If there is no specific logo for the Resource the logo of the Provider may be used.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	

Multimedia	Link to video, screenshots or slides showing details of the Resource.	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://www.lifewatch.eu/photo-video-gallery/
Multimedia Name	Short description of the Multimedia content	String (Max 100 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Website Videos and photos
Use Cases	Link to use cases supported by this Resource.	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://community.lifewatch.eu/working-groups/biodt/
Use Cases Name	Short description of the Use Case content	String (Max 100 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	BIODT: Biodiversity Digital Twin

3.3.3 Classification Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Scientific Domain	The branch of science, a scientific discipline that is related to the Service/ Resource.	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 9)	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	
Scientific Sub-domain	The sub-branch of science, the scientific subdiscipline that is related to the Service/Resource.	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 9)	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	
Category	A named group of Resources that offer access to the same type of Service/Resource or capabilities.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	

Sub-category	A named group of Service/Resources that offer access to the same type of Service/Resource or capabilities, within the defined Resource category	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	
Target Users	Type of users/customers that commissions a Provider to deliver a Service/Resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	
Access Type	The way a user can access the Service/Resource (Remote, Physical, Virtual, etc.)	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 10)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	
Access Mode	Eligibility/criteria for granting access to users (excellence-based, free-conditionally, free etc.)	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	
Tags	Keywords associated to the Service/Resource to simplify search by relevant keywords.	String (max 50 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Blockchain, Data analysis, Data gathering, Data visualisation, Modelling, Simulation tools, Tokenization, Virtual Research Environment

3.3.4 Geographical and language availability Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Geographical Availability	Locations where the Service/Resource is offered.	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 3)	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	<div style="display: flex; flex-wrap: wrap; gap: 5px;"> x Albania x Andorra x Austria x Germany x Greece x Hungary </div>
Language Availability	Languages of the (user interface of the) Service/Resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland

3.3.5 Resource Location Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Resource Geographic Location	List of geographic locations where data, samples, etc. are stored and processed	List of controlled values (See Appendix Table 3)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Spain

3.3.6 Contact Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Main Contact/Resource Owner - First Name	First Name of the Service/Resource's main contact person/manager.	String (max 20 words)	One	Mandatory	No	No	José Manuel
Main Contact/Resource Owner - Last Name	Last Name of the Service/Resource's main contact person/manager.	String (max 20 words)	One	Mandatory	No	No	Ávila Castuera
Main Contact/Resource Owner - Email	Email of the Service/Resource's main contact person/manager.	Email	One	Mandatory	No	No	josem.avila@lifewatch.eu
Main Contact/Resource Owner - Phone	Telephone of the Service/Resource's main contact person/manager.	String (max 20 words)	One	Mandatory	No	No	0034609788444

Main Contact/Resource Owner - Position	Position of the Service/Resource's main contact person/manager.	String (max 20 words)	One	Optional	No	No	Agroecology Coordinator
Main Contact/Resource Owner - Organisation	The organisation to which the contact is affiliated	String (max 50 words)	One	Optional	No	No	LifeWatch ERIC
Public Contact - First Name	First Name of the Resource's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Iria
Public Contact - Last Name	Last Name of the Resource's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Soto - Embodas
Public Contact -Email	Email of the Resource's contact person or a generic email of the Provider to be displayed at the portal.	Email	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	iria.soto@lifewatch.eu
Public Contact – Phone	Telephone of the Resource's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	0034616812551
Public Contact – Position	Position of the Resource's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Agroecology Project Manager
Public Contact – Organisation	The organisation to which the contact is affiliated	String (max 50 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	LifeWatch ERIC
Other Contact – Helpdesk email	The email to ask more information from the Provider about this Resource.	Email	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	iria.soto@lifewatch.eu
Other Contact – Security Contact Email	The email to contact the Provider for critical security issues about this Resource.	Email	One	Mandatory	No	Yes	securas@lifewatch.eu

3.3.7 Maturity Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Technology Readiness Level	The Technology Readiness Level of the Resource (to be further updated in the context of the EOSC).	List of controlled values	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	7 - system prototype demonstration in operational environment
Life Cycle Status	Phase of the Resource life-cycle.	List of controlled values	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Beta
Certifications	List of certifications obtained for the Resource (including the certification body).	String (max 100 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	No
Standards	List of standards supported by the Resource.	String (max 100 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Darwin Core, Ecological Metadata Language, INSPIRE, Others
Open Source Technologies	List of open-source technologies supported by the Resource.	String (max 100 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Blockchain, DRAMA, GIS, Keycloak, Kubernetes, Minio, NodeJS, Openstack
Version	Version of the Resource that is in force.	String (max 10 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	
Last Update	Date of the latest update of the Resource.	Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	11/05/2023
Change Log	Summary of the Resource features updated from the previous version.	String (max 1000 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	https://tesseract.lifewatch.dev/

3.3.8 Dependencies Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Required Resources	List of other Resources required to use this Resource.	Resource IDs	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	No
Related Resources	List of other Resources that are commonly used with this Resource.	Resource IDs	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://metadatalogue.lifewatch.eu
Related Installations	List of suites or thematic installation in which the Resource is engaged or Providers (Provider groups) contributing to this Resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Copernicus Climate Change Service
Catalogue	The Catalogue this Resource is originally registered at.	Catalogue ID	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	No

3.3.9 Attribution Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Funding Body	Name of the funding body that supported the development and/or operation of the Resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	European Commission (EC)
Funding Program	Name of the funding program that supported the development and/or operation of the Resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Other
Grant/Project Name	Name of the project that supported the development and/or operation of the Resource.	String (max 100 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	101058020 — AgroServ — HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01

3.3.10 Management Information

Field	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Helpdesk Page	The URL to a webpage to ask for more information from the Provider about this Resource.	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://www.lifewatch.eu/help-desk/
User information	Link to the Resource user manual and documentation.	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://training.lifewatch.eu/
Terms of Use	Webpage describing the rules, Resource conditions and usage policy which one must agree to abide by to use the Resource.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://workdrive.lifewatch.eu/external/1e06f91acf1d951698c67502238fdafc28de83caf61f2f4db6a52ca7b5849ed0
Privacy Policy	Link to the privacy policy applicable to the Resource.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://workdrive.lifewatch.eu/external/1e06f91acf1d951698c67502238fdafc28de83caf61f2f4db6a52ca7b5849ed0
Access Policy	Information about the access policies that apply	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://workdrive.lifewatch.eu/external/1e06f91acf1d951698c67502238fdafc28de83caf61f2f4db6a52ca7b5849ed0
Resource Level	Web Page with information about the levels of performance that a Provider is expected to deliver.	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Description showing the quality of the service
Training Information	Webpage to training information on the Resource.	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://training.lifewatch.eu/
Status Monitoring	Webpage with monitoring information about this Resource	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://status.lifewatch.dev
Maintenance	Webpage with information about planned maintenance windows for this Resource	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://status.lifewatch.dev

3.3.11 Access and Order Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Order Type	Information on the order type (requires an ordering procedure, or no ordering and if fully open or requires authentication)	List of controlled values	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Order required
Order	Webpage through which an order for the Resource can be placed	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	securas@lifewatch.eu

3.3.12 Financial Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Payment Model	Webpage with the supported payment models and restrictions that apply to each of them	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	-
Pricing	Webpage with the information on the price scheme for this Resource in case the customer is charged for it.	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	-

3.4 Metadata fields for Additional Information - Services

Figure 15 The M4C metadata fields for additional information on services provided

3.4.1 Marketing Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Main image for the descriptive sheet	This image will appear at the top of the description sheet and will be representative of the service.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	

<p>General description</p>	<p>What the service does. Short description.</p>	<p>String (Max 1000 words)</p>	<p>One</p>	<p>Mandatory</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>A Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is a versatile web-based workspace that allows data users to conduct data-related work more efficiently and fosters collaboration among diverse users, with the goal of generating new knowledge. A VRE typically encompasses centralized data access, processing, visualisation, result sharing, and other e-services. The VRE can be utilized to address both scientific and managerial inquiries and has applications across various fields, including agroecology. In agroecology, the VRE is a web-based workspace that provides data-users with a platform for networking, data gathering and integration, data analysis and visualisation, and artificial intelligence (AI) deep learning. The VRE allows researchers to identify and engage with their community while gathering and integrating data from various sources. It offers computing power through high data analysis capacities such as the Picasso supercomputing centre, storage capacity, and data maintenance. Additionally, researchers can share their data analysis processes, including workflows, models, and algorithms. The VRE also supports the use of AI-deep learning and digital twins for more advanced research. Moreover, the VRE in agroecology could offer training and capacity building opportunities and facilitate the dissemination and communication of research findings to relevant stakeholders. By providing a collaborative workspace and access to essential services, the VRE in agroecology enables data-users to conduct data-related work more efficiently and effectively, leading to the generation of new knowledge and advancements in the field of agroecology.</p>
<p>Functionalities it provides</p>	<p>Details of the regular and optional features provided by the service</p>	<p>String (Max 1000 words)</p>	<p>One</p>	<p>Mandatory</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>A Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is a versatile web-based workspace that allows data users to conduct data-related work more efficiently and fosters collaboration among diverse users, with the goal of generating new knowledge. A VRE typically encompasses centralized data access, processing, visualization, result sharing, and other e-services. The VRE can be utilized to address both scientific and managerial inquiries and has applications across various fields, including agroecology.</p>
<p>Users benefits</p>	<p>Eliminate undesired</p>	<p>URL</p>	<p>Multiple</p>	<p>Optional</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>In agroecology, the VRE is a web-based workspace that provides data-users with a platform for networking, data gathering and integration, data analysis and visualization, and artificial</p>

	outcomes, obstacles or risks							intelligence (AI) deep learning. The VRE allows researchers to identify and engage with their community while gathering and integrating data from various sources. It offers computing power through high data analysis capacities such as the Picasso supercomputing center, storage capacity, and data maintenance. Additionally, researchers can share their data analysis processes, including workflows, models, and algorithms. The VRE also supports the use of AI-deep learning and digital twins for more advanced research.
Users producing gains	Increase performance, social gains, positive emotions or cost saving	String (Max 100 words)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes		Moreover, the VRE in agroecology could offer training and capacity building opportunities and facilitates the dissemination and communication of research findings to relevant stakeholders. By providing a collaborative workspace and access to essential services, the VRE in agroecology enables data-users to conduct data-related work more efficiently and effectively, leading to the generation of new knowledge and advancements in the field of agroecology.
References	Customers, Communities, Publications	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes		https://community.lifewatch.eu/
Use cases	Short description of the Use Case content	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes		-

3.4.2 Location and Country

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Latitude	Latitude coordinate of the installation (in decimals: 60.924530 for 6055'8.3"N)	String (7 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Virtual access
Longitude	Longitude coordinate of the installation (in decimals: 11.451259 for 1127'04.5"E)	String (7 words)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Virtual access
Country Code	Country name abbreviation (France: FR)	Controlled values	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Virtual access

3.4.3 Dependencies Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Required /Related Resource	Is the resource is required to use the service or only a related resource?	List of controlled values	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Required
Required or Related Resource	Resource name	String (Max 100 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	N2 gaz for Picarro Oven
Measured parameter	Measured parameters by the required/Related Resource	String (Max 100 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	-
Precision / Sensitivity	Measuring range and precision	String (Max 100 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	-
Analytical Capacity	Resource measurement capacity (sampling frequency for continuous measurements, samples processed per day or per hour, ...)	String (Max 100 words)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Sampling frequency: 5 mins

Chapter 4

Conclusions and next steps

Conclusions and next steps

The M4C catalogue of services is built using the ISIA platform developed by CNRS, France, which already hosts service catalogues of AnaEE France, AnaEE ERIC and the EU-INFRA SERV projects AgroServ and IRISCC, proving evidence of fit-for-purpose functioning. Access to services by the users will be managed using the M4C CWE IT platform, requiring the development of a technical integration between both platforms (ISIA and CWE), which is already ongoing.

The M4C catalogue is being implemented in three subsequent phases: 1) Collect the data in structured description models; 2) Publish the data in catalogues accessible to all users; and 3) Make data interoperable with other scientific fields and their catalogues.

The catalogues of M4C installations and their services are already online (phase 1) and can be reached using the following links:

- [Installations](#)
- [Services](#)

They are currently being populated by the installation managers with all the information described in section 3 of this report (phase 2). For this, training sessions (of approximately one hour) have taken place to help managers navigate the data entry forms. The use of the tool remains very simple and does not require particular computer skills. It is also important to highlight that the catalogue model is an evolutive object and continuous feedback from providers and users will help us create a version that meets community needs.

The interoperability with other catalogues requires alignment with other initiatives (e.g. EOSC, ENVRI) and discussions to progress on this will occur during M4C execution (phase 3).

Furthermore, the development of the M4C catalogues of installations and services will be a continuous, iterative process that will consider new desired technical requirements throughout the M4C project period. This report will, therefore, be used as a starting point of a “living” document that is continuously updated over the course of M4C to reflect the different stages of the development of the M4C catalogue of installations and services.

Chapter 5

Appendix

Appendix

Providers Scientific Domain / Category Classification

Table 1 Providers Scientific Domain/Category Classification

No.	Scientific Domain	No.	Category	Description
1	Biological & Medical Sciences	1	Agronomy, Forestry and Plant Breeding Centres	Facilities that enable open field and forest experiments to test the impact of management practices and environmental conditions on soil, crop, and primary production. These include plants and trees ex-situ collections, experimental facilities for controlled crosses and propagation, and population genetics field testing. The facilities are relevant for Biological and Environmental Sciences.
		2	Animal Facilities	Facilities that provide the husbandry of animals and services to the biomedical research community are usually equipped with highly automated systems that provide the best possible conditions for animal reproduction and maintenance. The main activity is the reproduction and maintenance of animal stocks either of inbred strains or genetically engineered animals, such as transgenic and knockout mouse lines, or even chemically-induced mutants.
		3	Collections of Biological Resources (e.g. Microorganisms, Biobanks and Seed Banks)	Facilities for storage of collections of microorganisms, biological material and the associated data and information facilities for a population, or a large subset of a population, maintained under controlled conditions (temperature, humidity, atmosphere, etc.). The biological resources, including microorganisms, human/animal cells, tissue, blood and DNA, seeds of crops, trees and wild plant species, are conserved for their genetic endowment. Databases established on these provide holistic information on each accession with scientific descriptors, ethnobotanical/zoological/microbiological/medical knowledge, including to establish intellectual property rights and ownership over the biomaterial stored
		4	Bioinformatics Facilities	Bioinformatics facilities generate knowledge through computer analysis of biological data. These can consist of the information stored in the genetic code, but also experimental results from various sources, patient statistics, and scientific literature. Research in bioinformatics includes method development for storage, retrieval, and analysis of the data. Bioinformatics is a rapidly developing branch of biology and is highly interdisciplinary, using techniques and concepts from informatics, statistics, mathematics, chemistry, biochemistry, physics, and linguistics. It has many practical applications in different areas of biology and medicine.

5	Biological/Biomedical Engineering and Biotechnology/Nanotechnology Research Facilities	Facilities that are dedicated to application of concepts and methods of bioscience and/or nanoscience, and/or use of living systems and organisms to develop solutions to problems in life and preclinical sciences using engineering methodologies.
6	Biomedical Imaging Facilities	Facilities are equipped for the visualisation, characterisation and measurement of biological processes at the cellular and tissue levels in humans and other living systems.
7	Cell Culture Facilities	Facilities that are equipped to provide robust support for isolation and culture of a variety of cell lines (like mammalian and insect cell lines, mouse and human embryonic stem cells), including serum preparation, feeders, growth factors and mycoplasma testing, maybe on serum-based or serum-free media.
8	Environmental Health Research Facilities	Environmental health research addresses all potential hazards caused to a human being or an animal by external physical, chemical, and biological factors, and all the related factors impacting behaviours. It encompasses the assessment and control of those environmental factors that can potentially affect health. It is targeted toward preventing disease and creating health-supportive environments. This definition excludes behaviour not related to the environment, as well as behaviour related to the social and cultural environment, and genetics. This category includes toxicology and infectious diseases facilities as well as epidemiological study centres.
9	Genomic, Transcriptomic, Proteomics and Metabolomics Facilities	Multiple sites ranging from single laboratory DNA sequencing and RNA transcript analysis facilities run by biologists for their own department's research to high-throughput facilities aimed at providing a sophisticated service for a broad community of biologists run by informaticians, biologists and engineers. Proteomics: physical chemistry developments for clinical and biological applications getting access to protein networks linked to the physiological and pathological states of the cells. This includes nutrigenomics research.
10	Structural Biology Facilities	Facilities, which are equipped for visualisation, characterisation, and measurement of biological processes at the molecular level in humans and other living systems. Main technologies include protein crystallisation, X-ray diffraction, mass spectrometry, DSC.
11	Systems Biology/Computational Biology Facilities	Laboratories that combine all relevant scientific disciplines and the know-how to integrate experimental data with computational and theoretical approaches with the aim of targeting, understanding and engineering pathways, cells, organs and complete organisms.
12	Other	

2	Chemistry & Material Sciences	1	Analytical Facilities	All facilities where analytical tools are used are based on one of the following probes or methods: electrons, photons, neutrons, radio frequency, NMR, or analytical chemistry. It does include Surface Science Laboratories dedicated to analysis and characterization of surface and interface phenomena. Different users would come from the scientific domains Chemistry, Earth science, Bio-Medical (including forensic) science and different sensitivities (Analytical Chemistry, electron microscopy laboratories); NMR facilities; surface science laboratories; x-ray diffraction; Electron Microscopy Laboratories, aspects in life sciences, earth, forensics; Surface Science Laboratories.
		2	Chemical Libraries and Screening Facilities	Digital libraries related to chemistry as well as screening facilities.
		3	Intense Light Sources	All facilities that provide access to intense light radiation sources as used for lasers, synchrotrons, Free Electron Lasers. The facilities are relevant to the scientific domains of Physics, Chemistry, Bio-Medical Sciences, Earth and Environmental Sciences, Humanities & Arts, Information Science & Technology; Laser Sources for materials synthesis laboratories; Laser Sources for spectroscopy laboratories; Synchrotron Light Sources and X-Ray Diffraction Facilities.
		4	Intense Neutron Sources	Accelerator-based neutron source facility that provides the intense pulsed neutron beam.
		5	Materials Synthesis or Testing Facilities	All single or multi-sited facilities are run by engineers and materials scientists to process or test materials concerning predefined specifications. It includes testing and processing equipment, structural and properties characterization instruments. The facilities are relevant to the scientific domains of Engineering, Materials Sciences, Physics, and Chemistry.
		6	Pilot Plants for Process Testing	Plants where processes in biological or chemical systems, including bioenergy/biorefinery research and food processing research, are tested on a pilot level scale. Biology, Chemistry.
		7	Reference Material Repositories	Facilities providing materials with at least one standardized and fully described property that can be used in measurements e.g. as a standard for calibration of instruments or as a reference for measuring other materials.
		8	Other	
3	Earth & Environmental Sciences	1	Acoustic Monitoring Stations	Non-audible very low-frequency waves infrasound stations, (volcano meteors monitoring, avalanches, landslides); audible frequency stations and hydroacoustic stations (marine mammals, multi-beam, acoustic tomography, echosounders, sodar); high-frequency stations (T-phase stations).

2	Atmospheric Measurement Facilities	Meteorological stations (all physical parameters that can be observed); Global Atmospheric Watch (GAW); Airglow; Ionospheric stations (all sky cameras, ionospheric radar); brewers; lidars; chemical compositions, pollution and radionuclides facilities; This includes atmospheric test chambers, used to conduct controlled experiments for climate change research and atmosphere related problems.
3	Earth Observation Satellites	Including Optical-IR Earth Observation satellites and Radar Earth Observation satellites. Satellite imaging.
4	Earth, Ocean, Marine, Freshwater, and Atmosphere Data Centres	Installations for the exchange of earth, oceanographic, marine, freshwater and atmospheric data and information, and advisory services in the field of the earth, ocean, marine, freshwater and atmospheric data management. National Data Centres, Designated National Agencies for international data exchange and Satellite Data Centres represent the backbone of the data and information infrastructure. National networks are usually put in place to interconnect the data centres of major national institutes. The overall objective is to significantly improve the overview and access to data and data analysis from government and research institutes.
5	Environmental Management Infrastructures	Pilot facilities and experimental infrastructures for management, ecological restoration and environmental mitigation of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems in natural or degraded conditions (including hydrological and soil management field facilities; decontamination and bioremediation facilities and pilot plants).
6	In Situ Earth Observatories	Installations and sensor technologies deployed in situ to collect environmental data (including physical, chemical and biological observations) in support of terrestrial environmental research and management activities. These facilities, including ecological habitat field stations, provide a base for trans-disciplinary research and training, with access to terrestrial field sites for the survey and experimental opportunities and often supporting environmental observations and the collection of long-term time series data sets (i.e. on biodiversity).
7	In Situ Marine/Freshwater Observatories	Installations and sensor technologies deployed in situ to collect environmental data (including physical, chemical and biological observations) in support of aquatic environmental research and management activities. These facilities, including marine/freshwater research centres, provide a base for transdisciplinary research and training, with access to marine and freshwater field sites, and equipment (including research vessels that may carry large exchangeable underwater equipment/instruments) for the survey and experimental opportunities and often supporting environmental observations and the collection of long-term time series data sets (i.e. on biodiversity). Typical equipment includes Buoys; Argo; gliders; autonomous underwater vehicles; remotely operated vehicles (Victor); Tide gauges; deep-sea laboratories. Ship time

				for stock assessments, polar supply, naval research and educational courses and non-academic research are not considered in this context. For this inventory, the atmospheric measurement facilities are kept as a separate category. This implies that some marine research centres will also fall under this category if they host an atmospheric measurement site.
		8	Natural Collections History	Facilities that serve as a library of organisms that have lived and/or are living on Earth and curation sites for materials relevant for planetary exploration. They contribute to specific research and public education in an easily accessible venue.
		9	Other	
4	Information Science & Technology	1	Centralized Computing Facilities	Single-sited facilities with a centralized control that enable high-performance computing through supercomputers. These are relevant to all scientific domains.
		2	Communication Networks	Facilities responsible, at national or international levels, for the provision of data communications networks, capacity and services to the research and education community in all scientific domains. The networks typically connect other networks at international, regional or metropolitan level.
		3	Complex Data Facilities	Facilities to store huge and high dimensional data volumes and apply statistical methods to classify or cluster the data to extract valuable information. The facilities are relevant to Bio-Medical Sciences; Earth and Environmental Sciences; Physics; Astrophysics; Social Sciences.
		4	Distributed Computing Facilities	Facilities for virtualisation, grid and cloud computing, or capability computing that are loosely coupled, heterogeneous, and geographically dispersed distributed system with non-interactive workloads that involve a large number of files. They federate, share and coordinate distributed resources from different organisations that are not subject to centralized control, using open, general-purpose and in some cases standard protocols and interfaces to deliver non-trivial qualities of service relevant to all scientific domains.
		5	Software Facilities Service	Facilities that provide access to well fabricated software for modelling, simulation, development, control and optimization, including software libraries/ repositories or support services for the implementation of the software, their maintenance and adaptation to new hardware platforms as well consultation regarding the proper use of the software as well as training facilities for users. These are relevant to all scientific domains.
		6	Other	

5	Social Sciences	1	Data Archives, Data Repositories and Collections	A digital data archive is a centre of expertise in data acquisition, preservation, management, dissemination and promotion of access to the national and international collections and repositories of digital data. These types of RIs are particularly acute to the social sciences, which often rely on the aggregation of longitudinal data, and to the humanities, which often rely on preservation, but they can be relevant for other domains, particularly, the life and environmental sciences and the medical sciences.
		2	Data mining and Analysis (Methodological) Centres, including statistical analysis	Centres of expertise or methodological resources for extracting patterns from large data sets by combining methods from statistics and artificial intelligence. These RIs enable researchers to overcome the challenge of working with increasingly larger data sets. Data mining and statistical techniques populate every scientific domain but what counts as data is domain specific. Therefore, this category should be understood as specific to social sciences because it refers to data in the social sciences.
		3	National Statistical Facilities (offices)	Centres of expertise responsible for the collection and publication of statistics related to the economy, population and society at international, national and regional levels. These infrastructures have been traditionally created by the states but constitute as well powerful resources for social scientists in particular.
		4	Registers and Surveyed Studies/Databases	Organized and systematic collection of data (time or spatial series) for one or more purposes (research, evidence-based policy, non-governmental organisations) in digital form or not. These types of RIs are particularly acute to the social sciences, which often rely on the aggregation of masses of longitudinal data but they can be relevant for all the other domains, that is, the humanities, the life and environmental sciences, the physical sciences and engineering, and the medical sciences.
		5	Research Data Service Facilities	Facilities for clustering research data and making it permanently accessible, as well as facilities for the provision of all sorts of data services. These often include meta-infrastructures. These types of RIs are particularly relevant to Humanities and Arts; Social Sciences, Medical sciences.
		6	Other	
6	Other	1	Other	

- Source: MERIL [List of MERIL RI Categories](#)

Providers Type Classification

Table 2 Classification of Providers based on their Type

No.	Provider Type	Description
1	Single-sited	The Provider has one main physical location for users.
2	Distributed	The Provider has multiple physical locations but a unified management structure and a single coordination centre.
3	Mobile	The Provider is changing its physical location on a regular basis (e.g., satellites, research vessels)
4	Virtual	The Provider is exclusively an electronic resource/service.
5	Other	

Providers and Services / Resources Location Classification

Table 3 Providers and Services/Resources Location

Country Abbreviation	Country name
FR	France
IT	Italy
BE	Belgium
DK	Denmark
CZ	Czech Republic
PT	Portugal
UK	United Kingdom
DE	Germany
FI	Finland
ES	Spain
NL	Netherlands
RO	Romania
AT	Austria
BG	Bulgaria
IE	Ireland
IL	Israel
LT	Lithuania
NO	Norway
SE	Sweden
SI	Slovenia
CH	Switzerland
GR	Greece
PL	Poland
RS	Serbia
US	United States

Providers ESFRI Domain Classification

Table 4 Classification of Providers based on their ESFRI Domain

No.	ESFRI Domain
1	Energy
2	Environment
3	Health & Food
4	Physical Sciences & Engineering
5	Social & Cultural Innovation
6	Data, Computing and Digital Research Infrastructures
7	Other

Providers ESFRI type Classification

Table 5 Classification of Providers based on their ESFRI Types

No.	Provider ESFRI Status
1	RI is a node of an ESFRI project
2	RI is an ESFRI project
3	RI is an ESFRI landmark
4	Not an ESFRI project or landmark
5	Other

Providers Areas of Activity Classification

Table 6 Classification of Providers based on their Areas of Activity

No.	Provider Areas of Activity
1	Basic research
2	Applied research
3	Technological development

Providers Societal Grand Challenges Classification

Table 7 Providers Societal Grand Challenges Classification

No.	Provider Societal Grand Challenges
1	Health, demographic change and wellbeing
2	Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research and the Bioeconomy
3	Secure, clean and efficient energy
4	Smart, green and integrated transport

5	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials
6	Europe in a changing world – inclusive, innovative, and reflective societies
7	Secure societies – protecting the freedom and security of Europe and its citizens

Providers Sustainable, Development Goals Classification

Table 8 Providers Sustainable Development Goals Classification

No.	Sustainable Development Goals
1	No poverty
2	Zero hunger
3	Good health and well-being
4	Quality education
5	Gender equality
6	Clean water and sanitation
7	Affordable and clean energy
8	Decent work and economic growth
9	Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
10	Reduced inequality
11	Sustainable cities and communities
12	Responsible consumption and production
13	Climate action
14	Life below water
15	Life on land
16	Peace, justice and strong institutions
17	Partnership for the goals

Services / Resources Scientific Domain Classification

Table 9 Services/Resources Scientific Domain Classification

No.	Scientific Domain	Description	No.	Scientific Subdomain
1	Natural Sciences	Any of the sciences (such as physics, chemistry, or biology) that deal with matter, energy, and their interrelations and transformations or with objectively measurable phenomena (Merriam-Webster).	1	Computer sciences
			2	Information sciences
			3	Earth sciences
			4	Biological sciences
			5	Physical sciences
			6	Chemical sciences
			7	Biological and biomedical imagine
2	Engineering & Technology	The application of science and mathematics by which the properties of matter and the sources of energy in nature are made useful to people (Merriam-Webster).	1	Civil engineering
			2	Electrical, electronic and information engineering
			3	Mechanical engineering
			4	Aerospace engineering
			5	Chemical engineering
			6	Materials engineering
			7	Bioengineering and Biomedical engineering
			8	Environmental engineering
			9	Environmental biotechnology
			10	Industrial biotechnology
			11	Micro and Nanotechnology
3	Agricultural Sciences	Sciences dealing with food and fibre production and processing. They include the technologies of soil cultivation, crop cultivation and harvesting, animal production, and the processing of plant and animal products for human consumption and use (Britannica).	1	Agribusiness
			2	Agricultural Biotechnology
			3	Agricultural Chemistry
			4	Agricultural Economics & Social Science
			5	Agricultural Education
			6	Agricultural Geography
			7	Agricultural Marketing
			8	Agricultural Microbiology
			9	Agricultural Technology, Machinery & Mechanization
			10	Agroecology
			11	Agronomy (Includes Botany, Plant Physiology, Theoretical Production Ecology, Horticulture, Plant Breeding, Plant Fertilisation)
			12	Agrophysics
			13	Animal Science (Includes Animal/Poultry Breeding, Animal Husbandry, Animal Nutrition, Livestock Systems)

			14	Aquaculture, Fisheries & Marine Science
			15	Entomology & Plant Pathology
			16	Environmental Science & Agro-ecosystem
			17	Farm Management
			18	Food Science & Post-Harvest Technology
			19	Irrigation & Water Management
			20	Organic agriculture
			21	Range-Land Management
			22	Rural Buildings & Agro-Forest Land Planning
			23	Soil Science (Includes Biodiversity)
			24	Veterinary Sciences
			25	Waste Management
			26	Weed Science
			27	Food System
			28	Biological and biomedical imagine
4	Social Sciences	A branch of science that deals with the institutions and functioning of human society and with the interpersonal relationships of individuals as members of society (Merriam-Webster).	1	Psychology behavioural science
			2	Economics, finance and business
			3	Educational sciences
			4	Sociology
			5	Political sciences
			6	Social and economic geography
			7	Media and communications
5	Interdisciplinary	Involving two or more scientific disciplines/domains with methodologies and theories from all of them (Merriam-Webster).	1	Interdisciplinary
6	Multidisciplinary	Involving multiple disciplines/domains for research goals set under one thematic umbrella (Morton et al., 2015).	1	Multidisciplinary
7	Transdisciplinary	Integrating different scientific disciplines/domains and involving non-academic stakeholders in the research process (Morton et al., 2015).	1	Transdisciplinary

Source: MERIL: https://portal.meril.eu/meril/static/static_documents
https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/Scientific_Disciplines
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Agricultural_science
https://www.cun.it/uploads/storico/settori_scientifico_disciplinari_english.pdf
<https://www.britannica.com/science/agricultural-sciences/Major-divisions>
https://www.whed.net/search_by_fos.php?fos=Agriculture
<https://www.fao.org/agrovoc/releases>
Morton et al. (2015) <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26270306>

Services / Resources Access Type Classification

Table 10 Classification of services and resources based on their Access Type

No.	Access Type	Description
1	Remote	Services and Resources are delivered remotely with the use of a physical infrastructure. The user is able to remotely work with the physical RI without the need of physical presence.
2	Physical	Services and resources require a physical presence of the user. The user can only access the RI if he is physically present in the specific location that the RI is offered.
3	Virtual	The service/resource is delivered through a virtual infrastructure that the use may access virtually through the web or an intranet.
4	Mail-in	Samples are sent in to for e.g. analysis and the results are returned to the user without the user actually accessing the RI
5	Other	

